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Nature for insurance,
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CONCEPT NOTE

BOOSTING FLOOD RESILIENCE

through controlled flooding,
community insurance and
Nature-based Solutions

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Introduction

Flood risk in Italy is increasing significantly due to climate change, which is intensifying rainfall trends and leading to more frequent and intense extreme precipitation events. At the same time, changes in rainfall distribution are being observed, with a tendency towards fewer moderate events in certain areas.

This evolving pattern increases hydrogeological risk, contributing to longer dry spells alternating with short, intense rainfall episodes, which in turn amplify the occurrence of floods and landslides ([EUCRA, 2024](#)). The extreme flood events that struck the Emilia-Romagna region between 2023 and 2024 are emblematic of this trend.

In May 2023, unprecedented precipitation—two intense rain episodes within just 15 days—led to an accumulation of 400–450 mm of rainfall, causing 23 rivers to overflow and 13 to reach alert levels. The event resulted in 50 floods across 42 municipalities and more than 370 landslides, with severe damage to infrastructure, 36,600 people evacuated, and 17 fatalities. In some areas, the return period of these events exceeded 500 years.

However, only 16 months later, between 17 and 19 September 2024, another flood event affected the same area, recording precipitation totals between 150 and 300 mm, with peaks of up to 360 mm in some locations.

Currently, almost 7 million people (11.5% of the Italian population) live in flood-risk areas, while over 640,000 businesses (13.4% of the total) are located in high flood-risk zones ([ISPRA, 2021](#)). Despite the growing exposure and increasing risk, insurance coverage in Italy remains limited and fragmented. Most insurance policies are optional and offered as extensions of property or fire insurance policies.

A recent report by IVASS (2024) shows that only a small proportion of households and enterprises have flood insurance. The insurance market is characterised by high premiums, numerous exclusions, and complex contractual terms, which limit accessibility. In response to increasing risks and low coverage penetration, the 2024 Budget Law introduced an obligation for businesses to purchase insurance policies against catastrophic events, including floods, by 31 March 2025.

As flood risk rises, traditional hydraulic protection systems may prove increasingly ineffective. Properties located in vulnerable areas are at risk of facing prohibitive insurance costs, declining property values, and greater risk of mortgage defaults ([Gourevitch et al., 2023](#)).

Structural flood defences are progressively showing their inadequacy, as extreme events exceed their design thresholds, exposing the fragility of engineered waterways.

In this context, strategic land-use planning and a shift towards controlled flooding measures and Nature-based Solutions (NbS) may represent an innovative and advantageous approach to flood risk management.

Rural areas can function as natural buffers to protect densely populated urban centres with high-value properties and infrastructure. When carefully designated and managed, these areas can absorb excess water, reduce surface runoff, and preserve biodiversity, while supporting sustainable water and land management—through, for instance, the restoration or creation of wetlands, artificial basins, or levee setbacks.

As highlighted by the Italian Centre for River Restoration ([CIRF, 2023](#)), flood resilience requires giving more space to nature, prioritising river restoration, floodplain reconnection, and NbS over rigid artificial defences, which in the long term may increase vulnerability. However, in Italy, controlled flooding operations have so far been limited to structural measures such as flood storage basins. Controlled overflow areas have only recently become part of a reconstruction plan in Emilia-Romagna, led by the Po River Basin Authority.

The plan foresees the widening of embankments, expansion of river basins, and lowering of floodplains to enhance the natural retention capacity of rivers, as well as compensation schemes for farmers who make their land available for such purposes.

Context

The scheme proposed here has been developed and adapted for a specific area of northern Italy—the Po River Basin District—and in particular for the regions of Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, and Lombardy. Its objective is to test its operational, financial, and regulatory feasibility within current institutional and legislative frameworks.

In Italy, flood risk management is embedded in a multilayered and fragmented regulatory system that integrates national legislation, regional regulations, and European directives (see Box 1). The Environmental Code (Legislative Decree 152/2006) assigns regional and river basin authorities the responsibility for hydraulic risk management, including the identification, mapping, and safeguarding of hydrogeological risk areas (Articles 67 and following), in line with the Flood Risk Management Plans (PGRA) and the EU Floods Directive (2007/60/EC).

Governance levels and key actors in flood risk management

European level

The European Commission defines strategies for flood risk management and requires Member States to adopt Flood Risk Management Plans (FRMPs) in accordance with Directive 2007/60/EC (the Floods Directive).

National level

The Ministry of Environment and Energy Security (MASE) and the Civil Protection Department define national policies on flood risk management, coordinate emergency responses, and oversee the implementation of EU directives (Legislative Decree 152/2006 – Environmental Code; Legislative Decree 1/2018 – Civil Protection Code; Law 225/1992 on Civil Protection).

District (river basin) level

The Po River Basin District Authority, together with other basin authorities, is responsible for developing and implementing FRMPs, identifying priority areas for flood retention and risk mitigation, and monitoring the implementation of flood risk reduction measures, in compliance with Directive 2007/60/EC.

Regional level

The regional governments of Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, and Veneto—together with their respective Regional Civil Protection units—plan and manage flood defence infrastructure, authorise controlled flooding operations and emergency interventions, and provide financial incentives through the Rural Development Programmes (PSR) (Legislative Decree 152/2006; Legislative Decree 1/2018, and specific regional laws: L.R. 31/2008 – Lombardy; L.R. 21/2000 – Emilia-Romagna; L.R. 45/1980 – Veneto).

Local level

Reclamation Consortia (ConSORZI di Bonifica) and Municipalities manage and maintain the secondary water network and cooperate with regional and basin authorities to implement the measures defined in the FRMPs (L.R. 31/2008 – Lombardy; L.R. 7/2003 – Emilia-Romagna; L.R. 13/2002 – Veneto), in coordination with Provincial Territorial Coordination Plans (PTCP) and Municipal Land Use Plans (PGT).

Emergency level

In case of emergencies, the Civil Protection Department, Public Works Authorities (Genio Civile), Law Enforcement, and Fire Brigades are responsible for managing emergency flood operations. Under high-risk conditions, they may authorise extraordinary controlled flooding operations, in derogation from the normal provisions of FRMPs, as foreseen by Legislative Decree 1/2018 (Civil Protection Code) and Law 225/1992.

Currently, the regions of Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, and Lombardy have identified several priority areas for the creation of flood retention basins along major rivers such as the Adda, Oglio, Panaro, and Brenta. However, none of these regions has formally designated specific zones for controlled flooding, relying instead on temporary and exceptional measures, often applied in agricultural or low-risk areas when necessary. ▼

While there is no national law specifically regulating flooding easements, some Italian regions, such as Emilia-Romagna, have developed guidelines for their establishment and for determining the related compensation. In cases where an easement is imposed, Article 44 of Presidential Decree 327/2001 provides that compensation is due to the owner of the affected land, although the exact calculation methods are not detailed.

Although flood retention areas are recognised as key tools for hydraulic risk mitigation, controlled overflow operations often require complex authorisation and coordination processes involving multiple entities, including regional authorities, water boards (WBs), the Public Works Authorities (*Genio Civile*), and the Civil Protection Department.

The management of controlled flooding and compensation for landowners whose properties are temporarily flooded represent complex legal challenges. The Presidential Decree 327/2001 regulates expropriation for public utility, including the possibility of imposing easements on private property for public interest purposes.

Established practice suggests that the indemnity is calculated as a percentage of the expropriation compensation, depending on the degree of restrictions imposed on the property. Therefore, the establishment of flooding easements requires careful legal and procedural assessment, taking into account both national expropriation regulations and specific regional provisions, to ensure fair compensation for affected landowners.

Proposed solution

This concept note proposes a community insurance scheme to be purchased by authorities responsible for flood risk management (e.g. WBs) to reduce the financial and civil liability risks associated with controlled flooding operations.

The scheme envisions a system in which hydraulic risk management authorities purchase a collectively financed insurance policy to cover the costs of controlled flooding and thereby reduce overall flood risk. This model represents a risk-sharing mechanism designed to protect downstream communities exposed to flood hazards.

Community Insurance against Disasters

Community insurance is a collective insurance model managed by local authorities, communities, or governmental organizations to protect groups of people and assets within vulnerable communities against specific types of risks. Unlike individual policies, it is based on a risk-sharing mechanism that reduces costs and improves access to insurance coverage. Moreover, it encourages risk reduction measures at both individual and collective levels.

Community insurance complements the traditional insurance market by providing additional or alternative protection through customizable models tailored to the needs of different communities. Among these, the aggregator model, illustrated in the image and used as a reference for the scheme developed here, envisions the community being represented by a structured entity with an existing organization capable of negotiating coverage terms with insurance companies.

In this model, the institution representing the community purchases disaster insurance collectively, finances it through contributions or other mechanisms, ensures that costs and benefits are fairly distributed, and plays an active role in implementing protection and risk reduction measures.

The proposed scheme aligns with and leverages several existing or emerging elements within the regulatory, policy, and financial landscape, including:

- **The EU Floods Directive and agricultural land-use policies**, such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023–2027, require allocating at least 4% of farmland to non-productive elements for rewilding purposes.
- **The development of new insurance schemes**, considering the potential future expansion of mandatory flood insurance beyond businesses to include hydraulic risk management authorities.
- **The consolidation of incentive mechanisms and financial tools** for valuing ecosystem services, including biodiversity credits, payments for ecosystem services (PES), and environmental restoration funds to compensate landowners contributing to NbS implementation and ecological conservation.
- **Recent regulatory developments**, such as the EU Nature Restoration Law, which promote floodplain reconnection, adaptive water resource management, and ecological restoration.
- **The potential evolution of the mandate of hydraulic risk management authorities**, such as Reclamation Consortia (CdB), from a traditional resource and risk management model to that of ecosystem service providers.

Such an expansion of their mandate would allow them to continue performing their core functions while taking on new responsibilities in implementing, managing, and financing NbS. In some territories, certain CdBs have already begun this transition.

For instance, the **Consorzio di Bonifica Acque Risorgive** in the Venice Lagoon area has initiated collaborations with municipal administrations in its jurisdiction to provide land stewardship and governance tools such as Water Management Plans (*Piani delle Acque*).

Core Components

Hydraulic Risk Management Authorities as Insured Parties and Community Aggregators

Hydraulic Risk Management Authorities as Insured Parties and Community Aggregators Reclamation Consortia (CdB)—or other hydraulic risk management authorities—would be responsible for purchasing insurance policies covering the costs associated with controlled flooding.

The insurance policy could be financed through an additional fee collected by the CdB from property owners within their jurisdiction. These authorities would act as aggregators and intermediaries between the community and the insurer, with the responsibility to:

- (a) inform and engage citizens about costs, benefits, and insurance options;
- (b) collect contributions to finance the insurance policy; and
- (c) ensure that costs and benefits are fairly distributed among community members and territories.

Although hydraulic risk governance in Italy is complex and fragmented—with responsibilities distributed among different authorities according to regional legislation—CdB represent strategic actors for several reasons. They manage a wide range of water bodies to ensure hydraulic safety, water drainage, and irrigation of agricultural land. ►

Their competences vary by region, and in some cases, they operate under specific agreements with regional and municipal authorities for managing major water networks.

To fulfil these functions, they build and maintain the hydraulic and river infrastructures required. As public entities under private law, CdB collect contributions from the communities they serve. Their capillary presence and direct relationship with landowners, businesses, and administrations make them key enablers for a community-based risk-sharing system.

A major advantage in involving CdB in this scheme lies in their classification plan (*piano di classifica*), which determines the contribution of each property according to the level of benefit received from CdB activities. This is based on parameters such as flood risk level, property type (urban, agricultural, residential), and property size.

This well-established system would facilitate scheme implementation by reducing administrative complexity, positioning CdB as suitable managers of contribution mechanisms and ensuring smooth adoption by other authorities.

Moreover, the territorial data underlying the classification plans and their transparent contribution criteria make them adaptable and replicable by other authorities (e.g. municipalities, basin authorities) for financing insurance policies. This would guarantee an equitable and transparent cost distribution. It would also be essential to recalibrate and align contributions to

reflect new risk-reduction services, accounting for costs incurred (e.g. loss of productive agricultural land by farmers, who already bear higher contribution levels) and benefits received (e.g. greater protection for downstream urban property owners who benefit less from other CdB services such as irrigation).

Controlled Flooding as a Risk Reduction Measure

Controlled flooding involves the intentional diversion of river water into designated areas to relieve hydraulic pressure during heavy rainfall events, thereby mitigating flood risk in downstream urban areas and reducing potential damages and losses.

The proposed scheme aims to go beyond the traditional concept of flood retention basins by converting agricultural or rural land into floodable zones integrated with NbS. Designation would occur at critical flood-prone points—near drainage channels—on a provincial or sub-basin basis, potentially aligned with the CAP target of 4% of agricultural land set aside for rewilding.

If properly planned and combined with NbS (e.g. wetland restoration, agroecological landscape design), this approach can improve soil fertility, increase biodiversity, and provide other ecosystem services.

However, it entails operational costs, including water diversion, post-event restoration, and insurance coverage for accidental damages.

The objective is to transform hydraulic authorities such as CdB from simple water-risk managers into stewards of the territory and the ecosystem services it provides.

Scope and Characteristics of the Insurance Policy

The proposed insurance system could cover various aspects related to controlled flooding, including:

- Operational costs, such as infrastructure interventions and water diversion operations.
- Compensation for landowners, recognising their contribution to flood risk reduction.
- Civil liability coverage, for unintentional damages to third parties or properties.
- Post-flood restoration and NbS maintenance, including post-event water pumping, sludge removal, and ecosystem restoration.

A parametric insurance policy (see Box 3) would ensure quick and transparent compensation based on measurable thresholds (e.g. rainfall levels, exceedance of critical river stage thresholds, soil hydrological response under pre-existing conditions such as drought), which would trigger controlled flooding measures and avoid administrative delays.

Parametric Insurance

A **parametric insurance policy** is a type of insurance coverage that provides a predetermined payout in the event of a loss. It is automatically triggered when an external and objective index (or parameter) exceeds a certain predefined threshold (the trigger).

The main area of application for parametric insurance is climate risk, as extreme events are becoming increasingly intense, frequent, and often devastating in their impacts. Examples include protection against natural catastrophes (such as earthquakes or hurricanes) and against damage or production losses in agriculture caused by catastrophic events (e.g. droughts or hailstorms).

Parametric policies avoid the need for costly damage assessments or use advanced technological tools to quantify losses. Unlike traditional insurance—where compensation is based on documented damage assessments—parametric insurance does not require the insured party to prove that a loss has occurred. The payout amount is pre-established and is automatically disbursed once the specified index (parameter) in the coverage has been exceeded.

Parametric insurance is characterized by low operational and administrative costs, which result in more affordable premiums, as well as by simplicity, flexibility, and transparency regarding the payout amount and the speed of compensation.

The involvement of Civil Protection and environmental authorities would be essential to define the activation parameters of the policy, maintaining the accidental nature of the hydrometeorological event. Although controlled flooding is intentional, the “accidental” aspect must refer to the meteorological parameters that necessitate the operation.

To incentivise insurance companies, the risk management authority could purchase collective policies on behalf of the served community, ensuring a minimum coverage level. Alternatively, controlled flooding could be included under civil liability and accidental damage coverage for risk management entities.

Compensation and Financing of NbS

A key aspect of the proposed scheme concerns compensation mechanisms and the financing of NbS. To ensure landowners’ participation and promote the conversion of floodable areas into restored or naturalised zones, appropriate compensation and incentive mechanisms must be established.

Since these areas would lose part of their agricultural productivity, participation must remain economically viable through dedicated funding and incentives. As WBs may not have the authority to directly finance such investments, additional financial instruments or funding sources should be identified or activated. Among these, possible mechanisms include:

- Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) – compensating landowners for their contribution to flood risk reduction and ecosystem restoration.
- Biodiversity credits – monetising the ecological conversion of land into functional habitats.
- Instruments under the CAP 2023–2027 and regional Rural Development Programmes (PSR) – supporting agricultural practices that reduce hydraulic risk (e.g. vegetated buffer strips).
- Tax reductions and economic incentives – for landowners participating in the scheme.

Land-use conversion could occur on a voluntary basis, involving landowners through adequate compensation—potentially exceeding lost revenues—to incentivise their cooperation and support. Adopting a community insurance model would make it possible to include both those who benefit from controlled flooding (e.g. downstream communities) and those who make their land available for it, according to a principle of collective solidarity. This approach would provide both economic advantages and formal recognition of the risk mitigation services provided by participating landowners.

NbS could also be integrated into insurance pricing models as a measure that demonstrably reduces risk and, consequently, potential damages. However, as of now, there are no widely accepted standards for quantifying the value of ecosystem services—particularly in terms of effective risk reduction, taking into account quality of implementation and maintenance—that can be translated into insurance premium reductions. At the European level, a common methodology for correlating the adoption of adaptation measures with a reduction in insurance costs is still lacking.

Functioning and Governance

The governance of the community insurance scheme would be based on a structured collaboration between key actors in flood risk governance, the insurance sector, and private stakeholders, ensuring effective coordination.

The model envisions a mechanism in which WBs implement controlled flooding measures to mitigate flood risk in the communities they serve.

To cover operational costs, infrastructure damages, and civil liability, WBs would subscribe to a collective insurance policy financed through an additional contribution paid by consortium members, calculated according to the level of benefit each property owner receives from the flood risk reduction measure (as established in the classification plan).

The insurance policy protects WBs from such costs, ensuring that they can continue their normal functions after flood events.

At the same time, lands designated for controlled flooding would be renaturalised through the adoption of NbS, providing multiple benefits, such as improved ecosystem services and potential economic incentives for participating landowners. Below is reported the role of the various actors.

WATER BOARDS

- Implement controlled flooding and other adaptive measures to reduce flood risk and potential damages to the communities they serve.
- Purchase the community insurance policy through an additional fee on the consortium contribution, calculated based on the benefit derived from the controlled flooding measure.
- Act as intermediaries between landowners, local communities, and insurance companies.
- Ensure an equitable distribution of costs and benefits, and manage resources for post-flood restoration and NbS maintenance.

REGIONAL GOVERNMENT

- Define incentives for participating landowners (e.g. access to PSR funds).
- Supervise the management of controlled flooding areas and designate suitable zones through spatial planning tools (Provincial Territorial Coordination Plans – PTCP, Municipal Land Use Plans – PGT).
- May act as co-insurers alongside WBs to expand risk coverage.

RIVER BASIN AUTHORITIES

- Collaborate with regional governments to identify and designate areas suitable for controlled flooding.

CIVIL PROTECTION DEPARTMENT AND PUBLIC WORKS AUTHORITIES

- Activate extraordinary flooding operations during emergencies.
- Define risk management criteria and threshold parameters for flood control operations.

INSURANCE COMPANIES

- Develop parametric flood insurance products, potentially integrating NbS into premium-setting criteria.

LANDOWNERS AND FARMERS

- Provide land for controlled flooding operations in exchange for financial compensation.
- Participate in the implementation and maintenance of NbS.

Conclusions

The combination of challenges and opportunities emerging from discussions with insurance companies, regulatory authorities, WBs, and regional institutions confirms the potential of this scheme as an effective instrument to support controlled flooding operations and the integration of NbS in flood risk management.

If well designed, parametric insurance coverage can deliver benefits for all involved stakeholders.

Exposed communities would experience reduced flood risk; insurance companies would gain a new business line with a broader customer base and lower payouts thanks to risk mitigation; public administrations would reduce public spending on flood damage and post-disaster recovery; and landowners and farmers would benefit from multifunctional land conversion, economic incentives, and financial compensation.

The formal involvement of the Civil Protection Department, River Basin Authorities, and other environmental agencies would ensure clear rules for the activation of controlled flooding under defined risk conditions, which would also serve as triggers for indemnity payments.

Integrating NbS into insurance pricing models will require further standardisation and evaluation of ecosystem service benefits, but it represents a major opportunity to reward actors who contribute to risk reduction.

Expanding the role of WBs as ecosystem service providers and community aggregators would, in turn, require appropriate regulatory and operational evolution.

However, such a shift offers promising perspectives for enhancing the long-term resilience and adaptive capacity of territories. ■